

The need for social services at home for the elderly, an idea conceived in the education system as a necessity of modern times

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Abstract

Aging can be considered not only from the perspective of the individual as it is also a phenomenon of the whole population. The role of the family as the main institution of care for the elderly is coming and going, this is related to the loss of family tradition and the embrace of individualistic values offered by today's modern society. In Albania, the problems of care for the elderly will increase. And this conclusion is reached taking into account the very bad situation of the elderly nowadays. In this context, the number of elderly people receiving care outside the family is increasing significantly, while the residential capacities are the same. This article aims to find out the most preferred services for elderly nowadays, which enable them to continue living in their community, not necessarily by being accommodated in residential services. The working methodology consists of combining qualitative and quantitative analysis based on primary and secondary data, which create the possibility of multidimensional analysis and provide robust conclusions related to the research question. (for quantitative approach) In order to maximize the comparability of the data, the essential conditions of the study were applied in the most similar way possible in all ESS participating countries, (for qualitative approach) consisted of practicing the interview - pre-test - with individuals over the age of 65 in a suburban area of Tirana. Based on interviews conducted and other studies, it turned out that

home services are the preferred choice of elders, which enables them to continue living in their family environment. The service can be provided in different environments which include institutions or home environments.

Key words: elderly, aging, home services

Introduction

The world's population is aging in all regions of the world. Huge developments in technology, medicine, and public hygiene over the last 100 years have resulted in an increase in people living longer than ever before, with good health and the perspective of a more active long life in old age. (Asghar Zaidi November 2015). This trend coupled with a decline in fertility is resulting in a rapidly growing population of individuals older than 60 years old, in many parts of the world. Currently, individuals over 60 years old outnumber children under the age of five. By 2050, the number of these individuals will have increased and exceeded those under the age of 15. Active aging includes the continuation of present life in family and society, preventing age inequalities, which shows that according to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, human rights are rights attributed to every individual regardless of age, nationality, race, language, gender, sexuality or ability. The increase of the demographic perspective of the elderly in our country is always making more evident the start of the phenomenon of "population aging". In these conditions, the need for access and integration of care services for the elderly is raised. Albania in 2011 continued to have the youngest population on the European continent, except for Turkey, Ireland, and Iceland. The rate of aging of the Albanian population during the last decade has been the highest on the continent except for Lithuania. Compared to 28 EU countries, the population of Albania had an average age of 35.3 years old, in 2011; while the average of 28 EU countries was 41.2 years old. While in 2001 in Albania the average age was 30.6 years old, EU countries had an average age of 38.3 years old. Throughout this decade, the population as a whole has aged on average 4.7 years in Albania, while in EU countries by 2.9 year. In our society care for the elderly is generally seen as a family matter. The family has been the institution which has been seen as the best alternative to care for the elderly, in special cases or lack of family the second alternative for the care of the elderly has been the asylum or today called the "Home for the Elderly" ". The role of the family as the main institution of care for the elderly is coming and going, this is related to the loss of family tradition and the embrace of individualistic values offered by today's modern society. In this context, the number of elderly people

receiving care outside the family is increasing significantly, while the residential capacities are the same. Social protection structures and service structures for the elderly, in conditions when the aging population is on the growing trend are facing difficulties. Coping with them in these social protection systems, with their current capacities, is impossible. In all EU countries, the responsibility for providing and spending on long-term care is divided into four sectors:

- Family and informal care sectors
- State or public sector
- The sector of voluntary and non-governmental organizations
- Private sector or care market

In France, residential service is seen as a good alternative for the elderly who need constant medical care, while the number of elderly people receiving home care has increased. Most of the elderly prefer to stay in their homes, where they get to know their neighbours and can associate memories with every part of the accommodation and facilities around them, rather than going to a residential institution.

There are large differences in the use of long-term care services in Germany, depending on social status, ethnicity, and gender. Those in a higher social position are more likely to use home-based services provided by private institutions, while those in a lower social position are more likely to use cash compensation. Although in Germany the network of private service providers for the elderly is expanding more and more, where the most preferred service remains the home service. Formulated in 2008 for this purpose it is noted as follows: “To ensure that for persons with chronic disorders of a physical, intellectual or psychological nature for a long time, a high-quality care is available and that the cost of this care is socially acceptable.” In the Netherlands, a long-term public care insurance system has been in place since 1968, focusing not only on care for the elderly but on all citizens in need of such complex services.

Another help for the elderly who choose to live in their own homes can come from Local Agencies for the Elderly, where the elderly themselves can call for needed help. On this basis, this paper aims to propose and evaluate the following alternatives:

1. *Home services for the elderly living alone as a good alternative to delaying or avoiding institutional residential care.*
2. *Home assistant service for the elderly living alone, which provides assistance in daily activities such as washing / cleaning the environment and clothes or other personal items of the elderly, food, assistance in monthly payments such as water, electricity, friendly visits, etc.*

In these suggestions and alternatives the questions that are presented for discussion throughout the paper are:

- *How can institutional residential care for the elderly be postponed or minimized?*

Study objectives and research question

By strengthening the role of family and home services, as well as applying other alternative services such as home services, home assistant service, assisted living, it is possible to relocate the residential service as a last resort for the care of the elderly. In Albania due to the traditional culture of providing “forced” parental care, although the percentage of older people living alone in Albania is lower than in many western countries (UN, 2009), the impact of living alone on the elderly is most clearly reflected in society. However, with changes in lifestyle and family values, improvements in living conditions, the trend towards nuclear families and growing population departures at a young age, changing lifestyle arrangements and the number of older people living it is only growing. Thus from the census in 2001 to that of 2011, the number of elderly people living alone has increased from 5 to 8 percent expressed this in absolute numbers from 16.8 thousand in 2001 to 24.3 thousand in 2011. As previously explained, as a result of the change in the lower age of marriage and the higher life expectancy of females, older women are more likely to live longer alone. Thus 77 percent of the elderly living alone are female. The paper then focuses on identifying those social protection services that can be easily applied in our country. In response to this, the paper is directed based on the search for:

Is the application of integrated services a desirable service by the elderly?

Methodological platform

The methodology of this paper will be based on the three-dimensional research approach using qualitative and quantitative research techniques. Quantitative research will be based on primary and secondary data. Thus the main axes of research will be:

- Desk Analysis/literature review for quantitative secondary data analysis. Based on the existing “Micro-Level” data sources of the “Quality of Life” (CeJ) of the elderly by creating an “Inventory of existing data” in function of the work. Thus we can mention the data which can be considered as the main axis that have as source the Responsible Statistical Authority in Albania, the National Institute of Statistics (INSTAT).

- Analysis derived from primary data obtained from the European Social Survey Database (ESS), (2014). ESS Round 6 of the main questionnaire conducted by the Center for Comparative Social Studies, City University London. Analysis of primary qualitative data for CeJ targeting the elderly in social service institutions as well as analysis of primary qualitative data based on the ZMET method. The research of this paper focuses on the service beneficiary/customer. According to this view, the beneficiary of customer service is the human being with hope, dreams, boredom, fear, desire, and hope. Designing research centered on the human being is not a new phenomenon. Many methods and techniques have been developed precisely to keep the service recipient at the center of development processes (Kano, 1984), (Vogiazou et al., 2006), (Hutchinson et al., 2003).
- Qualitative analysis through ZMET Technique. This analysis is based on a new technique developed by Gerald Zaltman - professor emeritus at Harvard University. ZMET is based on the hypothesis that all human beings think in the form of metaphor and this leads to a deep structure of culture in order to understand and influence behavior.

Sample: The individual sample taken for this study was determined to consist of 60 elderly people currently in service institutions for the elderly. Of these 29 were male and 31 female. The selected sample (60) flows as a result of the sensitivity of the topic under study. The literature on services market studies and analysis argues and suggests that very small samples, even in the case of countries with large and heterogeneous populations, provide a variance of over 85% in content and emotion related to the variables required, associated with the product (Zaltman 2003). In order to conduct the interview, the heads of the institutions and the respective service employees introduced the interviewers to the beneficiaries of the institution. The staff significantly facilitated the construction of the relationship between the interviewer and the interviewee. This is as a result of respectful relationships built by service recipients for service. The staff also made it possible to create conditions for confidential space throughout the interview.

Study participants

The study included key people of the social protection system for the elderly, as well as interviews with elderly persons who are currently beneficiaries in this system:

1. Elderly part of residential service.
2. Leaders of residential social protection institutions in the country.

3. Representatives from the Directorate of drafting social policies for this field, at the Ministry of Social Welfare and Youth.
4. Leader and specialist in the field at the State Social Service

Results and discussions

Within the context of the aging world population and the fragmentation of the family due to migration and emigration of young people, the elderly in Albania are more likely to face new challenges. Although family ties and devotion to caring delivery are still culturally supported, older people may face an increased risk of low CJ and the need for long-term health services as well as social care, especially for those living alone. Implementation of action plans of sectoral and cross-sectoral social protection strategies is a need and priority. The quantitative and qualitative analysis performed in this paper the data showed that elders prefer to live in their own home, so integrated social services, such as home service, are the most preferred but also offer a better quality of life for them. The results of the analysis show that it is necessary to improve overall satisfaction as a key indicator of assessing CJ perception, as well as approaches to improve seniors' satisfaction with general, family, economic and social conditions. In this context, the focus of policymakers should be on improving their incomes, increasing available resources, enabling them in social life, in transport and services, in social activities, and making the issue of aging a community issue affect the improvement of their CJ. At the individual level, most of the elderly in the age group 60-70 are active and want and can participate in various profitable activities, including agriculture, environmental protection, etc. As another indicator identified with a significant impact on the CJ, the self-reported health situation is another specific element that needs to be addressed. Providing services dedicated to needs, such as providing home care, services such as free health examinations, in-home delivery of medications, education programs for self-care and healthy living and disease prevention, as well as providing basic training to improve health perceptions are strategic interventions to improve CJ of the elderly.

Recommendations

- In the implementation of the Social Service reforms in Albania, the aim is to provide alternative services, up to the personalized home service, as an antidote against residentialism. Elderly social care programs should be

integrated with other rights programs such as those for poverty alleviation, women's empowerment, people with disabilities, and empowerment programs for marginalized groups.

- Family members are the leading providers of care for the elderly. Giving proper care to an elderly person at home requires special knowledge and skills. Therefore, short training for family members on "Caring for the Elderly at Home" can be planned. Health centers and health care providers can be trained to train coaches' (ToT) who can further train elderly family members in the community.
- National policies on aging, supported by home-based care, would highlight the importance of enabling the elderly to live close to the community, thus taking an important qualitative step in improving the elderly. What is required in this situation is a model that would enable aging through economic efficiency and sustainability.

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Leadership and its impact on the challenges of higher education _____

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Abstract

Leadership can be defined as the ability of a leader to influence his employees, in such a way that they cooperate and contribute to the efforts oriented towards the realization of the goals of the educational institution. One of the challenges of the institutions, implemented in the market, is the selection of leaders who will represent the mission and vision of the educational institution.

The vision and mission of an institution should be represented by a leader with a contemporary outlook, who conveys to employees an inspiring and collaborative organizational behavior.

One of the concerns of institutions in recent years is the inefficient and inefficient organization of work. Therefore, the current leaders, who enjoy this status, must leave these wrong structures, in order to create harmony and organization among their subordinates. Organizing work with deadlines and division of tasks according to the specializations of the employee, will bring productivity and achieve objectives in a timely manner.

In the conditions of comprehensive changes of society, economy and politics, throughout the process of democratization and the prospects of EU membership, higher education in Albania is in constant transformation and reform from a state-controlled system to a liberalized higher education.

Key words: work, leadership, team, Europe 2020 Strategy